

SOME EXPERIENCES IN SUSTAINABLE CONSUMPTION PRODUCTION OF JAPAN, LESSONS FOR VIETNAM

Phạm Tiến Dũng,

Dr., National University of Hanoi

Nguyễn Ngọc Tú

Dr., Ministry of Industry and Trade

Abstract

Sustainable production and consumption are among the key goals of the United Nations. Over the years, member countries have actively developed and enacted legal documents and implemented strong initiatives for sustainable production and consumption. Japan is one of the countries with the best sustainable production and consumption practices globally, with the participation of all stakeholders in society, including regulatory agencies, the business community, consumers, and the media. In Vietnam, government authorities have gradually translated sustainable development goals into legal frameworks. In the future, stronger engagement from various societal stakeholders, such as businesses, consumers, and the media, will be needed to achieve sustainable development goals.

Keywords: sustainable production, sustainable consumption, sustainable development.

I. Overview of Sustainable Production and Consumption

1. Sustainable Consumption

The term "sustainable" first appeared in documents in the early 1980s. In 1994, some scientists introduced the concept of sustainable consumption. Sustainable consumption is defined in various ways. However, most agree that sustainable consumption is a process aimed at meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (Brundtland, 1987; Quoquab Mohammad, 2020), linking individual and societal responsibility to the long-term consequences of current actions (Carmi & Arnon, 2014).

Sustainable consumption behavior is a multidimensional concept, simply understood as the actions of individuals or consumer groups in seeking, purchasing, and using products and services to minimize waste, ensure personal and community health, and protect the environment. Specifically, sustainable consumption behavior is structured into three components: (1) Economical consumption, involving the selection of products or methods that use less fuel, energy, water, and other resources, as well as reusable packaging; (2) Health-conscious consumption, including the choice of organic products, those with eco-labels, eating more fruits and vegetables, and reducing unhealthy components such as sugar and fats; and (3) Environmental compliance, demonstrated through actions like following waste sorting guidelines, maintaining cleanliness in residential areas, and avoiding the consumption of banned products.

According to the current common understanding: (i) Sustainable production involves the economical and efficient extraction of resources, reducing waste, and protecting the environment; (ii) Sustainable consumption refers to consuming products and services that meet needs efficiently while minimizing negative environmental, social, and economic impacts; (iii) Sustainable production and consumption provide the key to enabling communities and individuals to develop without

sacrificing quality of life and without jeopardizing the needs of future generations.

3. Legal Regulations on Sustainable Production and Consumption in Vietnam

Currently, Vietnam's legal system does not have a comprehensive regulation that covers all aspects of sustainable production and consumption. However, the legal provisions related to sustainable production and consumption are specifically outlined as follows:

Decision No. 76/QĐ-TTg dated January 11, 2016, of the Prime Minister, approving the National Action Program on Sustainable Production and Consumption until 2020, with a vision toward 2030.

Decision No. 622/QĐ-TTg dated May 10, 2017, of the Prime Minister, issuing the National Action Plan for the Implementation of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

Decision No. 681/QĐ-TTg dated June 4, 2019, of the Prime Minister, issuing the roadmap for the implementation of Vietnam's Sustainable Development Goals by 2030.

Decision No. 889/QĐ-TTg dated June 24, 2020, of the Prime Minister, approving the National Action Program on Sustainable Production and Consumption for the period 2021 - 2030.

Decision No. 1658/QĐ-TTg dated October 1, 2021, of the Prime Minister, approving the National Strategy for Green Growth for the period 2021 - 2030, with a vision toward 2050.

Additionally, in Clause 10, Article 3 of the 2023 Law on Consumer Protection, it is stipulated: "Sustainable consumption is the use of products, goods, and services that meet the consumption and living needs of individuals, families, agencies, and organizations in an efficient manner while minimizing negative environmental, economic, and social impacts."

II. Japan's Experience in Sustainable Production and Consumption

2.1. Japan's Eco-Label Program

Japan's Eco-Label Program (NST) is also established and managed by the Japan Environment Association (JEA), aligned with the principles and standards of the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 14020 and ISO 14024. The program aims to guide consumers toward choosing eco-friendly products and promoting a healthier lifestyle for the community and environment. The purpose of Japan's NST Program is to widely disseminate information about the environmental aspects of products and to guide the activities of businesses and consumers toward the formation of a sustainable society. The NST Program is voluntary and open to all small and medium-sized enterprises, with over 75% of the awards granted to these businesses.

In February 1996, the Green Purchasing Network was established by the Ministry of the Environment to promote green purchasing in Japan by providing information and guidance on green purchasing practices. To date, the network has conducted numerous activities, such as workshops, green exhibitions, the "Green Purchasing" award, and product information databases, achieving certain successes. As a result, all central government agencies have implemented green purchasing, and 100% of government agencies in 47 provinces and 12 designated cities have been instructed to practice green purchasing.

2.2. Enhancing Education and Communication through Local Government

In Japan, the policy on sustainable production and consumption (SCP) has been integrated into environmental policies and is concretized in the 5th Basic Environmental Plan approved in 2018 (UNEP, 2012). This plan considers the connections between environmental, economic, and social issues and is designed to promote a shift towards a circular society. This has

been achieved through the establishment of cooperative mechanisms among stakeholders to stimulate innovation and address socio-economic issues through environmental protection (IGES, 2019).

The Japanese government has utilized a traditional value known as "Mottainai" to promote its environmental policies, particularly concerning the "3Rs" (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle), and has made significant progress. "Mottainai" can be loosely translated as "waste not" – a traditional value that reflects respect for the environment. Local authorities have launched effective campaigns using "Mottainai." It has also been used to address the issue of food loss and waste (FLW).

The Japanese government promotes sustainable consumption by employing a systematic approach to balance social, economic, and environmental aspects within policy frameworks. The role of local government is crucial in implementing national policies, as evidenced by many success stories initiated by local authorities.

2.3. Circular Economy Model in Japan

In recent years, countries around the world have been shifting from the traditional linear economic development model to a circular economy. The traditional linear economy typically begins with the extraction of raw materials, followed by production, consumption, and ultimately disposal. This operational method leads to continuous resource exploitation and an increase in waste volume released into the environment. Therefore, to minimize environmental waste, many countries worldwide have taken the lead in establishing circular economy (CE) models and have achieved positive results. Japan is one of the leading countries in the world and in Asia in developing policies for implementing the CE model.

Figure: Diagram Describing Linear Economy and Circular Economy

In Japan, the transition to a circular economy (CE) began in 1870, but it only yielded results when the Effective Recycling Use Law was implemented in 1991.

Japan became the first country to enact CE legislation, with strategies developed to reduce dependence on input materials and energy-intensive industries, as well as

to enhance resource efficiency.

The development of the circular economy in Japan is supported by effective cooperation between the government, consumers, and producers. Consumers play a crucial role in separating recyclable materials, while producers are responsible for recycling waste and raw materials and manufacturing long-lasting products. The government, on the other hand, plays a role in creating a legal framework and encouraging material recycling.

Additionally, Japan encourages the issuance of green bonds to promote environmental development projects. The first green bond was issued in 2014 by the Japan Development Bank, and since then, the total issuance has increased. In 2017, the Ministry of the Environment announced the Green Bond Principles to ensure consistency with the Green Bond Principles issued by the International Capital Market Association (ICMA). Green bonds are permitted to be traded on stock exchanges.

The circular economy system in Japan has three main features:

Consumer-friendly recovery system: The system for collecting old devices for recycling is very comprehensive and easy to use. Old devices are collected by retailers either in-store or when delivering a new device. For old technology equipment, manufacturers may be required to collect them from homes by local authorities, or they can be taken to any post office for return. This habit has been established throughout Japan, leading to a widespread understanding and use of the circular economy concept.

Pre-paid consumer fees: For electronic devices, transportation and recovery costs are paid at the point

of purchase, and penalties for littering are also increased.

Co-owned recycling infrastructure: Laws require coalitions of manufacturers to operate dismantling facilities, ensuring they benefit directly from recovering materials and parts. Consequently, companies invest in long-term recycling infrastructure. Because they own both production and recovery facilities, companies send product designers to dismantling plants to save time when separating poorly designed products. Some companies even run prototypes through the dismantling process to ensure they can be easily recovered.

2.4. Behavioral change and Cool Biz campaign in Japan

The Cool Biz campaign is an initiative from Japan launched by the Ministry of the Environment in the summer of 2005 as a measure to reduce electricity consumption among the Japanese people by limiting the use of air conditioning. This is implemented by setting the standard temperature of office air conditioners to 28 °C (approximately 82 °F) and allowing relaxed dress codes during the summer within the Japanese government's administrative apparatus.

For example, government employees are not permitted to wear shorts, t-shirts, or exercise pants, but they are allowed to wear polo shirts or sneakers. The dress code regulations also apply to public facilities such as schools, community centers, and libraries, which are also required to set their thermostats above 28 °C. Subsequently, this campaign spread to the private sector, resulting in the fact that virtually all employees in Japan adhere to the same dress code rules.

Figure: Flyer for the Cool Biz Campaign in Japan to 28°C.

Since its inception, the Cool Biz campaign faced some criticism and skepticism regarding its applicability; however, it has become one of the most successful environmental initiatives in Japan. In its first year alone, the Ministry of the Environment estimated that the campaign reduced carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions by 460,000 tons. The Narita International Airport Corporation reported that in 2005, it cut CO₂ emissions by 28 tons and saved 5.7 million yen (approximately 47,300 USD) simply by setting the office temperature

III. Some Lessons on Sustainable Production and Consumption for Vietnam

Sustainable production and consumption are inevitable trends for any country in the world. This is one of the goals of the United Nations aimed at minimizing the negative impacts of production and consumption on the global living environment and promoting responsible consumption in the context of limited resources. To

achieve this, the involvement and cooperation of various stakeholders in society are needed, specifically as follows:

1. For Government Regulatory Authorities

1.1. Developing Legal Documents to Encourage Sustainable Production and Consumption

The government plays a crucial role in providing direction for the establishment of legal documents aimed at promoting sustainable production and consumption in line with healthy business trends and sustainable consumption in Vietnam. These strategies need to be specifically outlined in legal documents such as laws, decrees, circulars, or through the issuance of programs and projects to encourage businesses to adopt sustainable production practices and to motivate consumers to shift their behavior toward sustainable products. Incentive policies for businesses may include tax incentives, preferential loan policies, support for technology development, and assistance with factory space, gradually replacing current production methods.

1.2. Advocacy for Sustainable Production and Consumption

After establishing policies and programs for sustainable production and consumption, government regulatory authorities need to enhance communication about sustainable production, encouraging circular production models like those in Japan. At the same time, they should provide guidance and incentives for consumers to change their behavior toward choosing environmentally friendly products, prioritizing the use of sustainable products.

1.3. Monitoring the Implementation of Sustainable Production and Consumption

An important tool for government regulatory authorities is inspection and monitoring to ensure compliance with legal regulations regarding sustainable production and consumption. After establishing legal documents and providing guidance and direction for sustainable production and consumption, specialized government regulatory agencies need to strengthen inspections, monitoring, and enforcement of responsibilities related to sustainable production and consumption. They should strictly handle violations while also recognizing and praising exemplary cases of compliance with these practices, creating good models for other entities to reference and learn from.

1. Business Community

Sustainable consumption is not only a trend but also plays a crucial role in the sustainable development and growth of the economy as a whole, as well as the growth of the business sector in particular. On the other hand, businesses are also the most important entities in promoting sustainable consumption.

Participating in the process of promoting sustainable consumption requires businesses to invest in green, clean, and environmentally friendly infrastructure and technology. In practice, many companies have actively upgraded their machinery, equipment, and technology, not only to gradually adopt advanced management methods and improve their competitiveness in the market but also to reduce emissions step by step. This, in turn, enhances the value of products, fulfills

obligations to the state budget, and significantly contributes to the economic development achievements of the country. At the same time, it allows businesses to gradually fulfill their social responsibilities in various forms and degrees to protect the environment and take care of the material and spiritual well-being of their employees. This represents an organic relationship between business development and the orientation toward promoting sustainable consumption.

Businesses need to boldly transition from conventional production to green and clean production aimed at environmental sustainability. Consumers will not have products to use if businesses do not produce them. In addition to creating products, companies also need to implement advertising and trade promotion policies to gradually change consumer behavior toward green consumption.

2. Consumer Community

In the relationship between production and consumption, consumers play a crucial role in the existence and development of businesses. If consumers do not purchase the goods and products of a business, it means that the business will not be able to survive in the market. Conversely, if consumers trust and use the products and services of a particular business, it represents an endless resource for that company, leading to its growth. The same applies to sustainable production and consumption; sustainable production is a trend and a future-oriented approach for both businesses and consumers. However, in the initial stages, pioneering businesses will have to incur higher costs for production and product promotion. To move toward sustainable production and consumption, consumers themselves need to gradually change their behavior by supporting the consumption of green, clean, and environmentally friendly products.

3. Media and Press

Media and press agencies play a central role in conveying the messages of government regulatory authorities regarding sustainable production and consumption to various segments of society, as well as communicating businesses' messages to consumers. Given their importance, media and press agencies need to promptly update the policies and guidelines of the Party and the laws of the State to the relevant parties in society. They also help businesses bring sustainable products to consumers while analyzing and evaluating these products to gradually encourage consumers to shift their behavior toward choosing environmentally friendly products. Additionally, media outlets should regularly update consumers on businesses that offer quality, eco-friendly products, and timely warn consumers about goods and services that do not meet standards and may harm the environment.

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